

Correlation Between Self-Concept and Academic Achievement in Mathematics Among Senior Secondary School Students in Batagarawa Educational Zone, Katsina State

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Abstract

This study established Correlationhsip between self-concept and academic achievement in Mathematics among senior secondary school students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina state. The study developed two objectives, research questions and tested corresponding hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance, respectively. It adopts descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted of One Thousand Five Hundred and Eighty-Five (1585) which include 786 Male and 799 Female senior secondary school class two (SSS II) students in Batagarawa educational zone, katsina state public schools during the 2021/2022 academic session. Multistage sampling Technique was used to select the sample size of Two Hundred and Seven (207) class two (SSII) students during the 2021/2022 academic session in public schools in Batagarwa educational zone. A validated questionnaire titled Self-concept questionnaire (SCQ) with reliability index of 0.798 was used for data collection in this study. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions, while Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient and t-test (Independent sample) statistic was used to test the null hypotheses. The results revealed that there is no significant relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary Mathematics students in Katsina state, Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended that, orientation should be regularly given to students on how to improve their self-concept and academic achievement as it may help them elevate their performance in Mathematics.

Keywords: Self Concept, Academic Achievement, Mathematics and Students

Introduction

After More than a decade of neglect self-concept is enjoying renewed popularity and attention by both researchers and practitioners into self-concept research. There is growing awareness that of all the perception we experienced in the course of living, none has more profound significance than the perception we hold regarding our own personal existence, our concept of who we are and how we fit into the world self-concept is the information that we have about ourselves what we think we are like. Self-concept is person's perceptions of himself formed through experience and interpretations of the environment. Self-concept generally refers to the composite of ideas, feelings, and attitudes people have about themselves. Our self-perceptions vary from situation to situation and from one phase of our lives to another (Ajmal & Rafique, 2018).

The aim of education is to discover and develop the abilities and character of individual's in order to serve the society better. During most conversations, people deliberate and chat about self-concept and intelligence, you hear them saying "he is looking confident", "he possesses good qualities" "he is intelligent "he can do it better" and so on Experience develops Self-concept and yields the level of intelligence a person possesses in life. Having positive and better Self-concept makes students to show optimism about their potential for success in future. They show confidence and competence they believe in hard work, dedication, determination and commitment to school work. They always think about success and good qualities and strive for it. They are superior in themselves thinking if anyone else can do it, they can do it better, in all aspects of life. Globally, education is considered to be the most important instrument for change and national development. The educational institutions should emphasize intellectual activities, moral judgments, aesthetic judgments, self-realization, individual freedom, individual responsibility and self- control development.

The study of self-concept has awakened growing interest in psychological research of recent years. Despite the numerous studies devoted to it. However, it is difficult to find a unanimous, accepted definition of the term self-concept, given that it has been approached from different theoretical perspectives. However, there is agreement among the different researchers in that, the term self-concept has multidimensional nature in which global self-concept is on the top followed by academic, physical and social self-concept. Academic Self-concept helps the individual in various important moments of life; In judgment, in decision making and in other situations. Deshmukh (2010) believes that the self is responsible for many successes and failures, as it promotes a positive Self-Concept, promoting safety and personal trust to develop skills. Society plays a dominant role in shaping self-concept of a person. Self is in fact a complex whole, which consists of several parts and sub-parts which

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have functional inter-relationship. Self is not an inborn quality: it develops gradually as a result of social interaction. It is the totality of attitudes, Judgment and values of an individual relating to his behaviors, abilities and qualities. This means academic self-concept as the perception or structure that can include content, attitudes or evaluative judgments' and are used to make sense of the world, focus attention on one's goals and protect one's sense of basic worth. Each one has about himself, formed from experience and a relationship with the environment, where significant people play important role. Kumari & Chamundeswari (2013) in her study found that some psychological aspects like self-concept have great impact on the achievement of students and it helps in determining the level of competence among students' potentials. She also concluded that the way students behave in academic settings depends upon self-awareness. Individuals approach regarding his/her talents and hidden potentials strengthen his/her belief in self and the individual get better grades in school. Nwezeh (2011) also carried out studies on the effects of anxiety on school achievement and found that at the primary level, anxiety generally depressed scholastic achievement, and that school achievement tasks tend to lose their threatening implications as students gain experience in coping with them. Therefore, academic self-concept and achievement are dynamically interactive and reciprocal; each is mutually reinforcing that a positive (or negative) change in one facilitates commensurate change the other. Academic self-concept is more highly correlated with academic achievement than m general self-concept. Students with high self-concept approach school related tasks with confidence. Success in those tasks reinforces this confidence. The opposite pattern is likely to occur for children with low academic self-concepts.

The most critical measure of any educational system is the assessment of its students. The aim of any research is to determine the extent to which this objective is achieved. If not, why and what can be done to achieve it? The fact that modern education has different levels of aims suggests that we must measure the extent of its success in a variety of ways. The implication of this is that it is the level of objective that goes a long way to determine the term to use. In other words, it is the time frame that determines whether it is academic performance or achievement. Philosophers elucidated further that the performance of more than 645,000 children in 4000 public schools derived their education achievement through their performance scores over a long period of time. Cooper & Burgar (2010) defined academic performance as a quality of performance in terms of tasks and class exercises with academic content. It is a level of a given standard content and excellence; a qualified academic achievement. Mission and goals of the education system usually determine learning outcome. This suggests that learning outcome transcends cognitive assessment. It includes attitude and values. In research, learning outcome dwells on academic achievement and attitude of the students. therefore, this study set to find out the correlationhsip between self-concept and academic achievement in Mathematics among senior secondary school students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina state

Despite the efforts put in place by the teachers and parents, education planners in teaching and learning process, few students achieve higher grades in their academic pursuit. Some score averages while the vast majority scores below average. Nowadays, students face a lot of crises in knowing themselves, having negative image about themselves. They woefully failed at many times during assessment, including those students who are opportune to be in good learning environments. Students are unwilling to accept blame, some abhor competition, unable to accept praise and these students end up achieving nothing at last. They always think about failures and do not see themselves as capable or competent to succeed because of their inadequacies. Some students develop a dependent academic behavior, especially girls that during examinations they usually rely on the boys in their classes tor assistances. Such female students keep saying that boys are academically better because of traditional and family stereotype that males are superior to females. This indicates that there are some underlying factors in determining the academic success or failure of students that are at play. In view of this, various psychological and physiological factors are said to be contributing either positively or negatively to the academic achievement of students. These factors include: motivation, intelligence, self-efficacy, interest, personality, peer-group influences, adjustment behavior and parental socio-economic status. In schools, students are not given the opportunity to develop self-concept by not engaging them in tasks and skills which go beyond the mere playful expression of the pleasure, the child do not realize the need to work to recognition by striving to succeed in his academic achievement. As such, the child lack confidence in pursuing academic excellence and confidence in studies and therefore, develop a sense of inferiority complex which eventually leads to failure in school subjects, such as mathematics.

Objectives of the Study

1. Determine the relationship between student's self-concept and academic achievement in mathematics among senior secondary Schools in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State.

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2. Determine the difference in the academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between Self-Concept and academic achievement in mathematics among senior secondary School students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State?
2. What is the difference in the academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State?

Research Hypotheses

1. Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between self-concept and academic achievement in mathematics among senior secondary schools in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State.
2. Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State.

Methodology

This research employed descriptive survey research design in investigating the relationship between student's self-concept and academic achievement in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey design is a method of collecting information by interviewing or administering a questionnaire to a sample of individuals within a small range (Haruna, 2010). It is a design that gathers information about prevailing conditions or situation for the purpose of description and interpretation. This design aimed at studying the existing relationships, prevailing practices, beliefs and attitudes held, processes and effects of developing trends. Hence, primary sources of data are to be used. Primary sources of data include questionnaires. This research design is relevant to this study because the researcher used questionnaire to collect information which are the same instruments to be used in this research design. Population of the study consist of all public senior secondary school class two (SSII) students in Batagarawa educational zone, Katsina State during the 2021/2022 academic session. This make the total of (1585) in the seven (7) Secondary Schools in educational zone. This is in line with the contention by Kothari (2004) who defines the target population as the total number of respondents in the total environment of interest. Multistage sampling Technique was used to select the sample size of Two Hundred and Seven (207) class two (SSII) students during the 2021/2022 academic session in public schools in Batagarwa educational zone. First stage of the sampling technique was simple random which was used to select three schools out of the seven school. Second stage involved the use of Research Advisers' Table (cited in Haruna, 2010) to select the number of students based on the proportion of the population. For the purpose of data collection questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. The questionnaire entitled 'Self-concept Questionnaire' (SCQ) was developed by the researcher and was administered to the respondents who duly filled them on their own and provided the required data for the study. The information required was personal, factual or indicate an individual's feelings and attitude. The instrument was made up of two sections (A and B). Section (A) is about demographic information of the respondents. While section (B) contain 30 items to responded using Strong Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D), Strongly Disagreed (SD) which represent student's feelings on the items of the instrument. This instrument was used in the study to find out the relationship of students' self-concept and academic achievement which is determined through responses made by the students by shading or ticking the appropriate option. The SCQ was validated by three relevant experts and after pilot study, the SCQ reliability was found to be 0.798 which made the instrument acceptable for the study.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviations of relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students

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Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Self-concept	207	11.74	3.28
Achievement	207	20.61	5.30

Table1 present mean and standard deviations of relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State. Result obtained shows that the number of student self-concept is recorded as 207 and mean of 11.75 and standard deviations of 3.28, while academic achievement is recorded 207 and mean of 20.61 and standard deviations of 5.31.

Research Question 2:

What is the difference in the academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State?

Table 2: mean and standard deviations difference in the academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and social self-concept

Group	N	Mean	S D	SE
Physical	111	20.97	4.73	.44
Social	96	20.20	5.90	.60

Table 2 present mean and standard deviations of difference in the academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State. Result obtained shows that students with physical self-concept recorded a mean of 20.97 and standard deviations of 4.73, while students with social self-concept recorded a mean of 20.20 and standard deviations of 5.90.

Hypothesis Testing

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State.

Table.4: PPMCC of the relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students

Variables	N	Mean	SD	R-value	Alpha	P-Value	Decision
self-concept	207	11.7488	3.28791	0.50	0.05	0.47	Not significant
Achievement	207	20.6184	5.30838				

Table 4 present PPMC of the relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State. Result obtained shows that r-value is 0.50, while p-value is 0.47. P-value is greater than alpha, hence the difference is not significance. Consequently, null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State, Nigeria is retained.

Ho2: There is no significant Difference between academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State

Table 5: Independent sample t-test of difference between academic achievement of mathematics students with physical self-concept and their counter parts with social self-concept

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Variables	N	Mean	SD	T	Df	P-Value	Decision
Physical	111	20.9730	4.73375	1.03	205	.303	Not significant
Social	96	20.2083	5.90257				

Table 5 present independent sample t-test of difference between academic achievement of mathematics students with physical self-concept and their counter parts with social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State. Result obtained shows that t-value is 1.03, while p-value is 0.30. P-value is greater than alpha; hence the difference is not significance. Accordingly, null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant Difference between academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and their counter parts with social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State, Nigeria is retained.

Discussion of Findings

Finding shows that no significant relationship was observed between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State, Nigeria. This finding is in line with that of Obilor, (2012), who study the extent to which Self-concept of students' influence his subject choice and the results of the tests indicated that Mathematics Self- esteem is not significantly related to Mathematics Achievement. Otta, and Williams (2012) examined Self-concept and Vocational Interest among secondary school students the findings revealed that there is no significant relationship between self-concept and vocational interest. This means the development of Self-concept is a very important aspect of globalization, especially in the world today. Knowledge and awareness of Self-concept could help a person to be mentally prepared to face the challenges ahead.

Finding number two revealed that no significant Difference was found between academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and their counter parts with social self-concept in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina State, Nigeria. The results revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between self-concept and Academic achievement among students. This is in accordance with the study done by Crawford (2013) asserted that a significant relationship exists between students' social confidence and their academic achievement scores.

Conclusion

The present study was conducted to find out the correlationhsip between self-concept and academic achievement in Mathematics among senior secondary school students in Batagarawa Educational zone, Katsina state. therefore, Self-concept Questionnaire (SCQ) was developed, validated and used in the study. It was hypothesized that, there is no significant relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students' in Katsina State, Nigeria and that there is no significant relationship between academic achievement of senior secondary mathematics students with physical self-concept and social self-concept in Katsina State, Nigeria. The study revealed that, both self-concept and academic achievement have influence on achievement of students in Mathematics where female students perceived themselves with higher self-concept and academic achievement than the male students. Despite difference in self-concept and academic achievement, both students' performance did not differ significantly.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the following are hereby recommended:

1. Students should be guided how to adjust their self-concept to enhance their academic achievement in Mathematics.
2. Students should be encouraged and guided to have good academic achievement so as to enhance their performance in schools.
3. Parents should encourage their children to develop good academic achievement to improve their academic achievement in different subjects in secondary schools.
4. Modern instructional facilities or resources shall be made available including Audio-visual, and multi-media gadgets which would be in tandem with the 21st century global world. This would help in addressing individual variability and interest among the students with different academic achievement.
5. Orientation should be regularly given to students on how to improve their self-concept and academic achievement as it may help them elevate their performance in mathematics and in other subjects.

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